

C-IMMSIM simulation results

May 7, 2025

Abstract

This document includes the plots relative to the simulation and the outcome of the epitope/peptide prediction used.

Produced by the C-IMMSIM Online server available at
<http://c-immsim.iac.rm.cnr.it> (alias to <http://kraken.iac.rm.cnr.it/C-IMMSIM>)

CITATIONS: For publication of results, please cite the following:

Nicolas Rapin, Ole Lund, Massimo Bernaschi, Filippo Castiglione. Computational Immunology Meets Bioinformatics: The Use of Prediction Tools for Molecular Binding in the Simulation of the Immune System. PLoS ONE 5(4): e9862
doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0009862, 2010

A retrospective validation

In-silico evaluation of adenoviral COVID-19 vaccination protocols: Assessment of immunological memory up to 6 months after the third dose. P. Stolfi, F. Castiglione, E. Mastrostefano, I. Di Biase, S. Di Biase, G. Palmieri, A. Prisco. Frontiers in Immunology, 13 (2022) doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262>

An in vivo validation

Identification and validation of viral antigens sharing sequence and structural homology with tumor associated antigens (TAAs). C. Ragone, C. Manolio, B. Cavalluzzo, A. Petrizzo, A. Mauriello, M-L. Tornesello, F. M. Buonaguro, F. Castiglione, L. Vitagliano, M. Ruvo, M. Tagliamonte, L. Buonaguro. Journal for ImmunoTherapy of Cancer. 9:e002694 (2021)
<https://jitc.bmj.com/content/9/5/e002694>

Original C-IMMSIM model: www.iac.cnr.it/~filippo/c-immsim

GETTING HELP:

Scientific problems: Filippo Castiglione (filippo_dot_castiglione_at_cnr_dot_it)

Technical problems: Ilaria Gonnella (ilaria_dot_gonnella_at_cnr_dot_it)

Figure 1: Cell counts shown. Legend: Act=active, Intern=internalized the Ag, Pres II = presenting on MHC II, Dup = in the mitotic cycle, Anergic = anergic, Resting = not active.

Figure 2: Legend: symbols as figure above.

Figure 3: The virus, the immunoglobulins and the immunocomplexes.

Figure 4: Concentration of cytokines and interleukins. Inset plot shows danger signal together with leukocyte growth factor IL-2.


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15]      pos=1191 len=8      GAQSGGST
16]      pos=1211 len=15     EREDEDDWDEEDD
17]      pos=1333 len=12     GRRQRRRRSGDG
18]      pos=1398 len=22     KSSGGKGGSYSQAASSDSAQGS

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DoPeptideList_I:

Given the antigen injected creates the list of peptides for all the NumAgProts proteins and for all i.e., 4 MHCI molecules

Read class I peptide list from file? NO

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=====
Allele: A0201
Pseudo sequence: KAAHVEQRKAQTRTV
Threshold: 9.523800
Max score: 27.437000

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Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-070433_5_7KE0Z8RexF3P.FSA_1_001

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MARGLQGVMLRSFGARDHTATVIETISIAPHFVRVRMVSPTLFDQAEAEPAAWLRFWFPDPNGSNTFQRAYTISEADPA
AGRFVAVDVLHDPAGPASSWARTVKPGATIAVMSLMGSSRFDVPEEQPAGYLLIGDSASIPGMNGIETVPNDVPIEMYL
EQHDDNDTLIPLAKHPRLRVRWVRRDEKSLAEAIENRDWSDWYAWATPEAAALKCVRVRLRDEFQFPKSEIHAQAYWNA
GRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQPESAVPAPARGSWRAQAASRLAPLKLPLVLSGVLAAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRL
LVSGAGAHRLFTVGFVAVGLGTGALLAAALTLWLHVIDARFARALRRLSKLSRPLGWFTSRGSGSIKKLVTDITLA
LHYLVTHAVPDAVAAVVAPVGVLVYLFVVDWRVALVLFVLPVLYLTTSSLTIQSGPRIVQAQRWAEKMNGEAGSYLEGQ
PVIRVFGAASSFRRLDEYIGFLVAVQRPLAGKKTMLMDLATRPFVWLIATGTLVAVTHRMDPVNLLPFMFLGTTFG
ARLLGIAYLGGGLRTGLLAARHLQVTLDETELAVREHPREPLDGEAPATVVDHVTFGYRPGVPVIQDVSLTLRPGVTVA
LVGPSGSGKSTLALLARFHDVERGAIIRVGGQDIRSLAADELYTRVGFVLEQAQLVHGTAENIALAVPDAPAEQVQVAA
REAIHDRVLRPLPDGYDTVLGANSGLSGGERQLTIARAILGDTPLVILDEATAFADPESEYLVQQALNRLTRDRTVVI
AHLRHTITRADQIVVLDHGRIVERGTHEELLAAGGRYCRWLWDTGGSRVAVAAAQDGTMLWHAMPPELNTARLMAGAGP
APMLAAAAGWQTLAALDAQAVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGSDKALAAATPMVVWLQTASTQAKTRAMQATAQAAAYTQAMA
TTPSLPEIAANHITQAVLTATNFFGINTIPIALTEMDYFIRMWNQAALAMEVYQAEAVNTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQS
TTNPIFGMSPSGSSTPVGQLPAAATQLGQLGEMSGPMQQLTQPLQVTSLSFSQVGGTGGGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLS
NHPLAGSGSPSAGALLRAESLPGAGGSLTRTPLMSQLIEKPVAPSVMPAAAAGSSATGGAAPVAGAMGQGAQSGGSTR
PGLVAPAPLAQEREDEDDWDEEDDMSYMIATPAALTAATDIDGIGSAVSVANAAVAATTGVLAAGGDEVLAAIAR
LFNANAEEYHALSAQVAAFQTLFVRTLTGGCGVFRRRRGRQCVTAAEHRAAGARRRRRRSGDQWRRLRQQRHFHFCGGQ
PEFRQHSEHRRIVGIVAGLAVLAVVVIGAVVATVMCRKSSGGKGGSYSQAASSDSAQGSVSLTA

```

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

```

0]      pos= 26 score=0.002404 unnormalised=0.3592000000      SIAPHFVRV
1]      pos= 131 score=0.011675 unnormalised=1.7442000000      LLIGDSASI
2]      pos= 141 score=0.003857 unnormalised=0.5762000000      GMNGIETV
3]      pos= 289 score=0.001835 unnormalised=0.2742000000      KLPLVLSGV
4]      pos= 293 score=0.019326 unnormalised=2.8872000000      VLSGVLAAAL
5]      pos= 303 score=0.035478 unnormalised=5.3002000000      TLAQLAPFV
6]      pos= 306 score=0.014092 unnormalised=2.1052000000      QLAPFVLLV
7]      pos= 338 score=0.000162 unnormalised=0.0242000000      GLLGTGALL
8]      pos= 344 score=0.001173 unnormalised=0.1752000000      ALLAAALTL
9]      pos= 407 score=0.006401 unnormalised=0.9562000000      AVPDAVAAV
10]     pos= 411 score=0.015430 unnormalised=2.3052000000      AVAAVVAPV
11]     pos= 424 score=0.023637 unnormalised=3.5312000000      YLFVVDWRV
12]     pos= 495 score=0.006240 unnormalised=0.9322000000      RLDEYIGFL
13]     pos= 502 score=0.007411 unnormalised=1.1072000000      FLVAVQRPL
14]     pos= 561 score=0.011936 unnormalised=1.7832000000      RLLGIAYGL
15]     pos= 576 score=0.007699 unnormalised=1.1502000000      LLAARHLQV
16]     pos= 585 score=0.005778 unnormalised=0.8632000000      TLDETELAV

```

17]	pos= 653	score=0.004259	unnormalised=0.6362000000	TLLARFHDV
18]	pos= 730	score=0.009680	unnormalised=1.4462000000	RLPDGYDTV
19]	pos= 767	score=0.016301	unnormalised=2.4352000000	ILDEATAFA
20]	pos= 922	score=0.035532	unnormalised=5.3082000000	ALAAATPMV
21]	pos= 991	score=0.010256	unnormalised=1.5322000000	ALTEMDFI
22]	pos=1020	score=0.002177	unnormalised=0.3252000000	TLFEKLEPM
23]	pos=1229	score=0.030531	unnormalised=4.5612000000	YMIATPAAL
24]	pos=1265	score=0.014955	unnormalised=2.2342000000	VLAAGGDEV
25]	pos= -1	score=0.701775	unnormalised=104.8410000000	non-binding event

=====
Allele: A0203
Pseudo sequence: KAAHVEQRKKAQTRV
Threshold: 10.639400
Max score: 26.625000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-070433_5_7KE0Z8RexF3P.FSA_1_001

MARGLQGVMLRSFGARDHTATVIETISIAPIHFVVRVMVSPTLFDQAEAEPAAWLRFWFPDNGSNTFQRAYTISEADPA
AGRFVAVDVLHDPAGPASSWARTVKPGATI AVMSLMGSSRFVPEEQPAGYLLIGDSASIPGMNGI IETVPNDVPIEMYL
EQHDDNDTLIPLAKHPRLRVVRWVRREKSLAEAIENRDWSDWYAWATPEAAALKCVRVRLRDEFGFPKSEIHAQAYWNA
GRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQPESAVPAPAGSWSRAQAASRLAPLKLPLVLSGVLAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRL
LVSGAGAHRLFTVGFVAVGLLGTGALLAAALTLWLHVIDARFARALRRLSKLSRLPLGWFTSRGSGSIIKLVTDTLA
LHYLVTHAVPDVAVAVAVPVGVLVYLVFVVDWRVALVFGPVLVYLTITSSLTIQSGPRIVQAQRWAEKMNGEAGSYLEGQ
PVRVFGAASSFRRLDEYIGFLVAWQRPLAGKKTMLDLATRPATFLWLI AATGTLLVATHRMDPVNLLPFMFLGTTFG
ARLLGIAYGLGRLTGLLAARHLQVTLDETELAVREHPREPLDGEAPATVVFHDVTFGYRPGVPVIQDVSILTRPGVTVA
LVGPGSGKSTLALLARFHDVERGAI R VGGQDIRSLAADELYTRVGFVLQEAQLVHGTAENIALAVPDAPAEQVQVAA
REAQIHDRVRLRDPGYDVTLVGANSGLSGGERQLTIARA I LGDTPVLI LDEATAFADPESEYLVQALNRLTRDRTVLVI
AHLRHTITRADQLVVLHDHGRIVERGTHEELLAAGGRYCRWLWDTGQGSRAVAAAQDGT RMLWHAMPPELNTARLMAGAGP
APMLAAAAGWQTLAALDAQAVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGSDKALAAATPMVVWLQTASTQAKTRAMQATAQAAAAYTQAMA
TTPSLPEIAANHITQAVLTATNFFGINTIPIALTEMDFIRMWQAALAMEVYQAEAVNTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQS
TTNPIFGMPSPGSSSTPVGQLPPAATQTLGQLGEMSGPMQLTQPLQVTSLFSQVGGTGGGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLS
NHPLAGSGSPSAGALLRAESLPGAGSLTRTPMSQLIEKPVAPSVMPAAAAAGSSATGGAAPVGAGAMGGAQSGGSTR
PGLVAPAPLAQEREDEDDWDEEDWMSYMIATPAALTA AATDIDGIGSAVSVANA AAVAAATTGVLAAGGDEVLAATAR
LFNANAEEYHALSAQVAAFQTLFVRTLTGGCGVFRRRRGRQCVTAAEHRAAGARRRRRRSGDGQWRLRQQRHFHFCGGGQ
PEFRQHSEHRRIVGIVAGLAVLAVVVIGAVVATVMCRRKSSGGKGSYSQAASSDSAQGSVSLTA

Epitopes of protein 0 -----
0] pos= 26 score=0.007753 unnormalised=1.0016000000 SIAPHFVRV
1] pos= 131 score=0.017453 unnormalised=2.2546000000 LLIGDSASI
2] pos= 289 score=0.006530 unnormalised=0.8436000000 KLPLVLSGV
3] pos= 293 score=0.004363 unnormalised=0.5636000000 VLSGVLAAL
4] pos= 303 score=0.025318 unnormalised=3.2706000000 TLAQLAPFV
5] pos= 306 score=0.016114 unnormalised=2.0816000000 QLAPFVLLV
6] pos= 407 score=0.017020 unnormalised=2.1986000000 AVPDAAVAV
7] pos= 411 score=0.022345 unnormalised=2.8866000000 AVAAVAVPV
8] pos= 576 score=0.004943 unnormalised=0.6386000000 LLAARHLQV
9] pos= 730 score=0.007645 unnormalised=0.9876000000 RLPDGYDTV
10] pos= 863 score=0.005036 unnormalised=0.6506000000 AMPPELNTA
11] pos= 922 score=0.031642 unnormalised=4.0876000000 ALAAATPMV
12] pos=1229 score=0.022253 unnormalised=2.8746000000 YMIATPAAL
13] pos= -1 score=0.811583 unnormalised=104.8410000000 non-binding event

=====
Allele: B0702
Pseudo sequence: KAAREEQIKAQTRE
Threshold: 8.702800
Max score: 28.406000

MARGLQGVMRLRSFGARDHTATVIETISIAIPHVRVRMVSPITLFDQAEAEPAAWLRFWFPDPNGSNTFQRAYTISEADPA
 AGRFAVDVVLHDPAGPASSWARTVKPGATIAVMSLMGSSRFDPVEEQPAGYLLIGDSASIPGMNGIETVPNDVPIEMYL
 EQHDDNDTLIPLAKHPRLRVRWVRRDEKSLAEAIENRDWSDWYAWATPEAAALKCVRVRLRDEFQFPKSEIHAQAYWNA
 GRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQPESAVPAPARGSWRAQAASRLAPLKLPLVLSGVLAAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRL
 LVSGAGAHRLFTVGFVAVGLLGTGALLAAALTLWLHVIDARFARALRLRLSKLSRLPLGWFTSRGSGSIKLVDDTLA
 LHVLVTHAVPDAVAAVVAPVGVLYLFFVVDWRVALVLFPGPVLVYLTITSSLTIQSGPRIVQAQRWAEKMNAGEAGSYLEGQ
 PVIRVFGAASSSFRRRLDEYIGFLVAWQRLAGKKTLMDLATRPATFLWLI AATGTLVATHRMDPVNLLPFMFLGTTFG
 ARLLGIAYGLGGLRTGLLAARHLQVTLDETELA VREHPREPLDGEAPATVVFHDHVTFGYRPGVPVIQDVSLTLRPGTVTA
 LVGPGSGKSTLATLLARFHDVERGAIIRVGGQDIRSLAADELYTRVGFVLQEAQLVHGTAENIALAVPDPAEQVQVAA
 REAQIHDRVLRPLPDGYDTVLGANSLSGGGERQLTIARAILGDPVLI DEATAFADPESEYL VQALNRLTRDRTVLVI
 AHRLHTITRADQIVVLDHGRIVERGTHEELLAAGGRYCRWLDWTGGSRVAVAAAQDGTMLWHAMPPELNTARLMAGAGP
 APMLAAAAGWQTL SAALDAQAVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGSDKALAAATPMVVWLQTASTQAKTRAMQATAQAAA YTQAMA
 TTPSLPEIAANHITQAVLTA TNFFGINTIPIALTEMDYFIRMWQAALAMEVYQAETA VNTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQS
 TTNPIFGMSPSGSSTPVGQLPPAATQTLGQLGEMSGPMQQLTQPLQVTSLSFSQVGGTGGGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLS
 NHPLAGGSGPSAGALLRAESLPGAGGSLTRTPMSQLIEKVPVAPSVMPAAAAGSSATGGAAPV GAGAMGQAGSGGSTR
 PGLVAPAPLAQEREDEDDWDEEDDMSYMIATPAALTAATDIDGIGSAVSVANAAVAATTGVLAAGGDEVLAAIAR
 LFNANAEYHALSAQVAFAFQTLFVRTLTGGCGVFRRRRGRQCVTAAEHRAAGARRRRRRSGDGQWRRLRQQRHFHFCGGGQ
 PEFRQHSEHRRIVGIVAGLAVLAVVVIGAVVATVMCRRKSSGGKGSYSQAASSDSAQGSVSLTA

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos= 0	score=0.006274	unnormalised=1.1752000000	MARGLQGMV
1]	pos= 28	score=0.017404	unnormalised=3.2602000000	APHFVRVRM
2]	pos= 33	score=0.005142	unnormalised=0.9632000000	RVRMVSPITL
3]	pos= 77	score=0.007154	unnormalised=1.3402000000	DPAAGRFAV
4]	pos= 104	score=0.006834	unnormalised=1.2802000000	KPGATIAVM
5]	pos= 169	score=0.009968	unnormalised=1.8672000000	IPLAKHPRL
6]	pos= 174	score=0.028086	unnormalised=5.2612000000	HPRLRVRWV
7]	pos= 268	score=0.028406	unnormalised=5.3212000000	VPAPARGSW
8]	pos= 270	score=0.007379	unnormalised=1.3822000000	APARGSWRA
9]	pos= 286	score=0.018536	unnormalised=3.4722000000	APLKLPLVL
10]	pos= 290	score=0.017217	unnormalised=3.2252000000	LPLVLSGVL
11]	pos= 308	score=0.007811	unnormalised=1.4632000000	APFVLLVEL
12]	pos= 361	score=0.004266	unnormalised=0.7992000000	FARALRLRL
13]	pos= 417	score=0.002729	unnormalised=0.5112000000	APVGVLYVL
14]	pos= 508	score=0.030035	unnormalised=5.6262000000	RPLAGKKTLL
15]	pos= 522	score=0.007064	unnormalised=1.3232000000	RPATFLWLI
16]	pos= 578	score=0.010704	unnormalised=2.0052000000	AARHLQVTL
17]	pos= 622	score=0.004779	unnormalised=0.8952000000	VPVIQDVSL
18]	pos= 633	score=0.009226	unnormalised=1.7282000000	RPGTVTALV
19]	pos= 642	score=0.003701	unnormalised=0.6932000000	GPSGSGKST
20]	pos= 710	score=0.012685	unnormalised=2.3762000000	APAEQVQVA
21]	pos= 878	score=0.016443	unnormalised=3.0802000000	GPAPMLAAA
22]	pos= 880	score=0.004314	unnormalised=0.8082000000	APMLAAAAG
23]	pos= 961	score=0.007811	unnormalised=1.4632000000	TPSLPEIAA
24]	pos=1047	score=0.013416	unnormalised=2.5132000000	MPSGSGSSTP
25]	pos=1054	score=0.009311	unnormalised=1.7442000000	TPVGQLPPA
26]	pos=1059	score=0.035672	unnormalised=6.6822000000	LPPAATQTL
27]	pos=1082	score=0.011719	unnormalised=2.1952000000	QPLQVTSLS
28]	pos=1128	score=0.018264	unnormalised=3.4212000000	GPSAGAGLL
29]	pos=1163	score=0.020954	unnormalised=3.9252000000	APSVMPAAA
30]	pos=1167	score=0.021120	unnormalised=3.9562000000	MPIAAAAGSS
31]	pos=1233	score=0.035901	unnormalised=6.7252000000	TPAALTA AA
32]	pos= -1	score=0.559676	unnormalised=104.8410000000	non-binding event

=====
 Allele: B5301
 Pseudo sequence: KAAREEQIKTQTRTE
 Threshold: 8.175800
 Max score: 25.226000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-070433_5_7KE0Z8RexF3P.FSA_1_001

MARGLQGVMLRSFGARDHTATVIETISIAPIHFVVRVMVSPFLFQDAEAEPAAWLRFWFPDPNGSNTEFQRAYTISEADPA
AGRFVAVDVLHDPAGPASSWARTVKPGATI AVMSLMGSSRFVPEEQPAGYLLIGDSASIPGMNGI IETVPNDVPIEMYL
EQHDDNDTLIPLAKHPRLRVRWMMRDEKSLAEAIENRDWSDWYAWATPEAAALKCVRVRLRDEFQFPKSEIHAQAYWNA
GRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQPESAVPAPARGSWRAQAASRL LAPKLPLVLSGVLAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRL
LVSGAGAHRLFTVGF AAVGLLGTGALLAAALTLWLHVIDARFARALRLRLLSKLSRLPLGWFTSRGSGSIKKLVTDTLA
LHVLVTHAVPDAVA AVVAVPVGVLVYLVVDWRVALVLFPGPVLVYLTITSSLTIQSGPRIVQAQRWAEKMGNEAGSYLEGQ
PVIRVFGAASSFRRLDEYIGFLVAWQRPLAGKKTMLDLATRPATFLWLI AATGTLVATHRMDPVNLLPFMFLGTTFG
ARLLGAIYGLGGLRTGLLAARHLQVTLDETELAVREHPREPLDGEAPATVVFHDHVTFGYRPGVPIQDVSLTLRPGVTVA
LVGPSGSGSTLATLLARFHDVERGAIRVGGQDIRSLAADELYTRVGFVLEQAQLVHGTAENIALAVPDAPAEQVQVAA
REAIHQHRLRRLPDGYDTVLGANSGLSGGERQLTIARA ILGDTPVILDEATAFADPESEYLVQQALNRLTRDRTLVI
AHLRHTITRADQIVVLDHGRIVERGTHEELLAAGGRYCRWDGTGQSRVAVAAAQDGTMLWHAMPPELNTARLMAGAGP
APMLAAAGWQTL SAALDAQAVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGGSDKALAAATPMVVWLQTA STQAKTRAMQATAQAAAAYTQAMA
TTPSLPEIAANHITQAVLTATNFFGINTIPIALTEMDYFIRMWNQAALAMEVYQAEAVNTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQS
TTNPIFGMPSPGSSTPVQGLPPAATQTLGQLGEMSGPMQLTQPLQVTSLSFSQVGGTGGGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLS
NHPLAGSGPSAGAGLLRAESLPGAGSLTRTPMSQLIEKPVAPSVMPAAAAGSSATGGAAPVAGAGMGQAQSGGSTR
PGLVAPAPLAQEREDEDDWDEDDWMSYMIATPAALTAATDIDIGSAVSVANAAVAATTVGLAAGGDEVLAAIAR
LFNANAEEYHALSAQVAAFQTLFVRTLTGGCGVFRRRRGRQCVTAAEHRAGAARRRRRSGDGQWRLRQQRHFQCGGQ
PEFRQHSEHRRIVIGAVLAVLVVIGAVVATVMCRRKSSGGKGSYSQAASSDSAQGSVSLTA

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos=	23	score=0.016215	unnormalised=2.6242000000	ETISIAPHF
1]	pos=	44	score=0.009363	unnormalised=1.5152000000	DAEAEPAAW
2]	pos=	48	score=0.034920	unnormalised=5.6512000000	EPAAWLRFW
3]	pos=	59	score=0.036143	unnormalised=5.8492000000	DPNGSNTEF
4]	pos=	75	score=0.008411	unnormalised=1.3612000000	EADPAAGRF
5]	pos=	77	score=0.004697	unnormalised=0.7602000000	DPAAGRFAV
6]	pos=	91	score=0.054508	unnormalised=8.8212000000	DPAGPASSW
7]	pos=	112	score=0.006489	unnormalised=1.0502000000	MSLMGSSRF
8]	pos=	122	score=0.012835	unnormalised=2.0772000000	VPEEQPAGY
9]	pos=	149	score=0.012977	unnormalised=2.1002000000	VPNDVPIEM
10]	pos=	205	score=0.005216	unnormalised=0.8442000000	WATPEAAAL
11]	pos=	250	score=0.011420	unnormalised=1.8482000000	EPAATEPEV
12]	pos=	268	score=0.028623	unnormalised=4.6322000000	VPAPARGSW
13]	pos=	290	score=0.003221	unnormalised=0.5212000000	LPLVLSGVL
14]	pos=	522	score=0.007979	unnormalised=1.2912000000	RPATFLWLI
15]	pos=	544	score=0.018916	unnormalised=3.0612000000	DPVNLLPFM
16]	pos=	622	score=0.007144	unnormalised=1.1562000000	VPVIQDVSL
17]	pos=	731	score=0.009733	unnormalised=1.5752000000	LPDGYDTVL
18]	pos=	874	score=0.004592	unnormalised=0.7432000000	MAGAGPAMP
19]	pos=	946	score=0.018934	unnormalised=3.0642000000	QATAQAAAY
20]	pos=	950	score=0.004747	unnormalised=0.7682000000	QAAAAYTQAM
21]	pos=	956	score=0.002090	unnormalised=0.3382000000	QAMATTPSL
22]	pos=	964	score=0.008516	unnormalised=1.3782000000	LPEIAANHI
23]	pos=	974	score=0.005575	unnormalised=0.9022000000	QAVLTATNF
24]	pos=	1059	score=0.014189	unnormalised=2.2962000000	LPPAATQTL
25]	pos=	1082	score=0.004716	unnormalised=0.7632000000	QPLQVTSL
26]	pos=	-1	score=0.647830	unnormalised=104.8410000000	non-binding event

DoPeptideList_II:

Given the antigen injected creates the list of peptides for all the
NumAgProts proteins and for all i.e., 2 MHCII molecules

Read class II peptide list from file? NO

=====

Allele: DRB3_0101
Pseudo sequence: RVTLGRDAYW
Threshold: 2.631130
Max score: 27.850000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-070433_5_7KE0Z8RexF3P.FSA_1_001

MARGLQGVMLRSFGARDHTATVIETISIAIPHFRVVRMVSPTLFDQAEAEPAAWLRFWFPDPNGSNTEFQRAYTTISEADPA
AGRFVAVDVLHDPAGPASSWARTVKPGATIAVMSLMGSSRFDVPEEQPAGYLLIGDSASIPGMNGIETVPNDVPIEYML
EQHDDNDTLIPLAKHPRLRVRWVMMRDEKSLAEAIENRDWSDWYAWATPEAAALKCVRVRLRDEFKSEIHAQAYWNA
GRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQESAVAPARGSWRAQAASRLAPLKLPLVLSGVLAAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRL
LVSGAGAHRLFTVGFAAVGLGTGALLAAALTLWLHVIDARFARALRLRLSKLSRPLGWFTSRGSGSIKKLVTDTLA
LHYLVTHAVPDAVAAVVAPVGVLVYLVVDWRVALVLFPGVLYLTTITSSLTIQSGPRIVQAQRWAEKMNGEAGSYLEGQ
PVIRVFGAASSSFRRLDEYIGFLVAWQRPLAGKKTMLDLATRPATFLWLIATGTLVATHRMDPVNLLPFMFLGTTTFG
ARLLGIAYGLGGLRTGLLAARHLQVTLDETELAVREHPREPLDGEAPATVVDHVTFGYRPGVPIQDVSLTLRPGTVTA
LVGPGSGKSTLATLLARFHDVERGAIIRVGGQDIRSLAADELYTRVGFVLQEAQLVHGTAENIALAVPDAPAEQVQVAA
REAIHQHRLRRLPDGYDVTLVGANSGLSGGERQLTIARAALGDTPVLLDEATAFADPESEYLVQQALNRLTRDRTVLVI
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APMLAAAAGWQTLAALDAQAVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGGSDKALAAATPMVWVLTASTQAKTRAMQATAQAAAAYTQAMA
TTPSLPEIAANHITQAVLTAATNFFGINTIPIALTEMDFYIRMWQAALAMEVYQAETAVENTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQS
TTNPIFGMSPSGSSTPVGQLPPAATQTLGQLGEMSGPMQLTQPLQVTSLSFSQVGGTGGGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLS
NHPLAGSGSPSAGALLRAESLPGAGSLTRTPMSQLIEKPVAPVMPAAAAGSSATGGAAPVGGAGAMGQAGSGGSTR
PGLVAPAPLAQEREDEDDWDEEDWMSYMIATPAALTAATDIDGIGSAVSVANAAVAATTGVLAAGGDEVLAAIAR
LFNANAEEYHALSAQVAFAQTLFVRTLTGGCGVFRRRRGRQCVTAAEHRAAGARRRRRRSGDGQWRLRQRHFQGGGQ
PEFRQHSEHRRIVGIVAGLAVLAVVIGAVVATVMCRKSSGGKGSYSQAASSDSAQGSVSLTA

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

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2]	pos= 71	score=0.015026	unnormalised=3.7208700000	YTISEADPA
3]	pos= 83	score=0.003602	unnormalised=0.8918700000	FAVDVVLHD
4]	pos= 88	score=0.026292	unnormalised=6.5108700000	VLHDPAGPA
5]	pos= 114	score=0.003420	unnormalised=0.8468700000	LMGSSRFDV
6]	pos= 132	score=0.016015	unnormalised=3.9658700000	LIGDSASIP
7]	pos= 145	score=0.017069	unnormalised=4.2268700000	IIETVPNDV
8]	pos= 160	score=0.005265	unnormalised=1.3038700000	EQHDDNDTL
9]	pos= 161	score=0.004369	unnormalised=1.0818700000	QHDDNDTLI
10]	pos= 183	score=0.037894	unnormalised=9.3838700000	MRRDEKSLA
11]	pos= 195	score=0.008023	unnormalised=1.9868700000	ENRDWSDWY
12]	pos= 312	score=0.028885	unnormalised=7.1528700000	LLVELSRL
13]	pos= 368	score=0.001897	unnormalised=0.4698700000	RLLSKLSRL
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15]	pos= 393	score=0.005827	unnormalised=1.4428700000	VTDLTLALH
16]	pos= 404	score=0.001776	unnormalised=0.4398700000	VTHAVPDAV
17]	pos= 407	score=0.002790	unnormalised=0.6908700000	AVPDAVAAV
18]	pos= 426	score=0.037498	unnormalised=9.2858700000	FVVDWRVAL
19]	pos= 442	score=0.001231	unnormalised=0.3048700000	VYLTITSSL
20]	pos= 444	score=0.007624	unnormalised=1.8878700000	LTITSSLTI
21]	pos= 446	score=0.010802	unnormalised=2.6748700000	ITSSLTIQS
22]	pos= 468	score=0.003069	unnormalised=0.7598700000	MNGEAGSYL
23]	pos= 485	score=0.005298	unnormalised=1.3118700000	FGAASSSFR
24]	pos= 494	score=0.001857	unnormalised=0.4598700000	RRLDEYIGF
25]	pos= 502	score=0.001469	unnormalised=0.3638700000	FLVAWQRPL
26]	pos= 541	score=0.048595	unnormalised=12.0338700000	HRMDPVNLL
27]	pos= 584	score=0.032984	unnormalised=8.1678700000	VTLDETELA
28]	pos= 616	score=0.000928	unnormalised=0.2298700000	FGYRPGVPL
29]	pos= 624	score=0.037793	unnormalised=9.3588700000	VIQDVSLTL
30]	pos= 676	score=0.004761	unnormalised=1.1788700000	LAADELYTR
31]	pos= 687	score=0.029624	unnormalised=7.3358700000	FVLQEAQLV
32]	pos= 723	score=0.024059	unnormalised=5.9578700000	QIHDRVLR
33]	pos= 759	score=0.056312	unnormalised=13.9448700000	ILGDTPVLI

34]	pos= 766	score=0.047885	unnormalised=11.8578700000	LILDEATAF
35]	pos= 773	score=0.011169	unnormalised=2.7658700000	AFADPESEY
36]	pos= 790	score=0.051939	unnormalised=12.8618700000	LTRDRTVLV
37]	pos= 807	score=0.001191	unnormalised=0.2948700000	TRADQIVVL
38]	pos= 813	score=0.031913	unnormalised=7.9028700000	VVLDHGRIV
39]	pos= 838	score=0.010152	unnormalised=2.5138700000	RLWDTGQGS
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42]	pos=1012	score=0.003250	unnormalised=0.8048700000	YQETAVENT
43]	pos=1036	score=0.011016	unnormalised=2.7278700000	ASQSTTNP
44]	pos=1229	score=0.006622	unnormalised=1.6398700000	YMIATPAAL
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49]	pos= -1	score=0.267200	unnormalised=66.1680000000	non-binding event

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Allele: DRB1_0101
Pseudo sequence: KAFAHVEQRKAQTRV
Threshold: 2.392440
Max score: 26.461000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-070433_5_7KE0Z8RexF3P.FSA_1_001

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AGRFVAVDVLHDPAGPASSWARTVKPGATIIVMSLMGSSRFVPEEQPAGYLLIGDSASIPGMNGIETVPNDVPIEMYL
EQHDDNDTLIPLAKHPRLRVRVWRRDEKSLAEAIENRDWSDWYAWATPEAAALKCVRVRLRDEFGFPKSEIHAQAYWNA
GRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQPESAVPAPARGSWRAQAASRLAPLKLPLVLSGVLAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRL
LVSGAGAHRLFTVGFVAVGLLGTGALLAAALTLWLHVIDARFARALRLRLSKLSRLPLGWFTSRGSGSIKKLVTDDTLA
LHVLVTHAVPDAVAVVAVPVGLVYLVFVVDWRVALVFGPVLVYLTITSSLTIQSGPRIVQAQRWAEKMNAGEAGSYLEGQ
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ARLLGAIYGLGLRTGLLAARHLQVTLDETELAVREHPREPLDGEAPATVVFHDVTFGYRPGVPVIQDVSLLRPGTVTA
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REAIHQDRVLRPLDGYDVTGLGANSGLSGGERQLTIARAILGDTPVILDEATAFADPESEYLVQQALNRLTRDRTVLVI
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TTNPIFGMPSGSSTPVGQLPPAATQLGGLGEMSGPMQLTQPLQVTSLSFSQVGGTGGGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLS
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PGLVAPAPLAQEREDEDEDWDEEDWMSYMIATPAALTAATDIDIGSASVAVANAAVAATTGVLAAGGDEVLAATAR
LFNANAEEYHALSAQVAFAFTLFRVTLTGCGVFRRRRGRQCVTAAEHRAAGARRRRRRSGDQWRLRQQRHFHFCGGGQ
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Epitopes of protein 0 -----

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2]	pos= 42	score=0.006551	unnormalised=3.8285600000	FQDAEAEPA
3]	pos= 71	score=0.004327	unnormalised=2.5285600000	YTISEADPA
4]	pos= 111	score=0.006720	unnormalised=3.9275600000	VMSLMGSSR
5]	pos= 112	score=0.013043	unnormalised=7.6225600000	MSLMGSSRF
6]	pos= 130	score=0.008284	unnormalised=4.8415600000	YLLIGDSAS
7]	pos= 203	score=0.015851	unnormalised=9.2635600000	YAWATPEAA
8]	pos= 205	score=0.010060	unnormalised=5.8795600000	WATPEAAAL
9]	pos= 237	score=0.012439	unnormalised=7.2695600000	WNAGRAMGT
10]	pos= 276	score=0.027304	unnormalised=15.9575600000	WRAQAASRL
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13]	pos= 298	score=0.000761	unnormalised=0.4445600000	LAALVTLAQ
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16]	pos= 312	score=0.007020	unnormalised=4.1025600000	LLVELSRL
17]	pos= 316	score=0.002436	unnormalised=1.4235600000	LSRLLVSGA
18]	pos= 321	score=0.010396	unnormalised=6.0755600000	VSGAGAHRL
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39]	pos= 482	score=0.002155	unnormalised=1.2595600000	IRVFGAASS
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44]	pos= 519	score=0.003517	unnormalised=2.0555600000	LATRPF
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73]	pos= 874	score=0.009393	unnormalised=5.4895600000	MAGAGPAPM
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